

RICE DISEASE DETECTION USING ENSEMBLE METHOD

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Abstract—Rice is the most important food crop in India which covers 1/4th of the total cropped area. There are various disease that affect the paddy. This cause significant reduction in the production of the rice and it affect the food security of that region. The primary part where the disease initially visible is the leaf. Detecting the disease early is vital in order to stop its spread and minimize its impact. The proposed ensemble model consist of Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and K-Means Clustering with two classes of rice leaf disease – Bacterial Leaf Blight and Brown Spot using rice leaf disease dataset from Kaggle. The model has attained 75% accuracy while compared with traditional methods.

Keywords — Rice leaf disease, Ensemble, Convolutional Neural Network(CNN), K-Means Clustering, Image processing.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the most significant crops for human consumption is rice, which has a wealth of nutritional, commercial, and therapeutic uses. According to statistics data, 50% of the world's population consumes rice, and the world's rice output ranks third among food crops, after maize and wheat. On the other hand, rice infections have long afflicted all major rice-producing regions world wide. Illnesses possess the capacity to significantly reduce rice production and quality, hence threatening the global food supply. Therefore, regulating the spread of disease requires early detection and fast diagnosis of rice diseases in addition to preventative and control measures. The majority of plant disease signs are seen on leaves, which serve as the primary source of disease identification information.

Traditional method of detecting the disease by the naked eye is not much efficient as it is more time consuming and most of the disease should be diagnosed at the early stage of the leaves. The widespread implementation of the most recent computer-based identification system has been hindered by its significant environmental impact, slow detection rate, and limited accuracy. Consequently, the development of a technique for detecting rice diseases[1] quickly and accurately holds considerable importance.

Different machine learning[11] techniques and deep learning techniques can be used to detect the disease in rice leaves. Instead of using any one of the above method, it is better to use the combined model of both to increase the accuracy of prediction.

Ensemble methods refer to strategies designed to enhance the accuracy of model outcomes by amalgamating multiple models rather than relying on a single model. This aggregation of models notably boosts the precision of the results. By leveraging the diversity of different models, ensemble methods can mitigate individual model weaknesses and produce more accurate and robust predictions. Ensemble methods can be applied to various machine learning algorithms including decision trees, neural networks, and support vector machines. Common ensemble methods include bagging, boosting, random forests, stacking, and voting, each with its unique approach to combining models. Ensemble learning is widely used in various machine learning applications due to its ability to enhance predictive performance and improve model generalization.

The proposed system use the combination of CNN[6] model and K-Means Clustering. CNN is a type of deep neural network that is primarily used for image processing and classification tasks. CNNs are composed of multiple layers, including convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers. Convolutional layers apply a set of learnable filters to input data, enabling the network to learn hierarchical features directly from the raw data. Pooling layers decrease the spatial dimensions of feature maps generated by convolutional layers, aiding in the reduction of computational complexity and the prevention of overfitting.

Fully connected layers combine the features learned by previous layers to make predictions or classifications. CNNs typically end with one or more fully connected layers followed by a softmax activation function for classification tasks.

K-means clustering[10] is a widely used unsupervised machine learning algorithm utilized for dividing a dataset into a predetermined number of clusters. The algorithm operates through iterative steps where it assigns data points to the nearest cluster centroid and subsequently updates the centroids by computing the mean of the data points assigned to each cluster. K-means clustering is computationally efficient and scalable, making it suitable for large datasets with high-dimensional feature spaces. Together these models give the best output to the prediction.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Khan et al. [2] utilized a hybrid learning approach, incorporating Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), and Self-Attention (SA)

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Modules. Their model, designed for diagnosing rice leaf diseases using Mendeley data, achieved a training accuracy of 100% and validation accuracy of 97.51%, while achieving 100% accuracy on testing samples.

Zamani et al.[3] employ an image processing framework and machine learning to detect leaf disease. The segmentation of the image into numerous portions facilitates the use of the k-means algorithm to identify the boundaries of the image. Principal component analysis is used for feature extraction, and RBF-SVM, SVM, random forest, and ID3 algorithms are used for picture classification.

Multiple CNN classifiers were used by Dechant et al. [4] in their analysis of maize disease photos. The results of the experiment showed that 90.8% accuracy was achieved with just one CNN classifier. However, the accuracy rose to 95.9% when two first-level classifiers were used, and to 97.8% when three first-level classifiers were used.

Gautam V. et al. [5] presents the significance of early detection and classification of leaf diseases in paddy crops, emphasizing the crucial role of deep learning methods in agricultural research. It outlines the utilization of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) with transfer learning (TL) architectures, such as InceptionV3, VGG16, ResNet, SqueezeNet, and VGG19, for disease detection. The review highlights the proposed model's superior accuracy of 96.4%.

“Plant disease detection for paddy crop using Ensemble of CNNs” by Acharya A. et al.[6] uses five pre-trained Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architectures viz. GoogLeNet, ResNet, ShuffleNet, ResNeXt and Wide ResNet to predict three paddy leaf diseases viz Blast, Bacterial Leaf Blight and Brownspot. The model has an accuracy of 95.54%.

Pallapothala T. et al.'s work on rice leaf disease detection using CNN came to the conclusion that deep learning models outperform machine learning techniques. The investigation found that the VGG16 model has the lowest accuracy of 58.4% and the 5-layer convolution model has the highest accuracy of 78.2%.

Plant diseases are classified using a deep convolutional neural network (CNN) model in the Belmir M. et al.[8] suggested model. The programme makes use of the PlantVillage dataset, which consists of photos showing 14 different kinds of crop leaves—both damaged and healthy—grouped into 38 categories. The CNN model achieves 98.01% training accuracy and 94.33% test accuracy, according to experimental results. These results demonstrate how well the model works to identify leaf diseases early on.

"Prediction of Corn and Tomato Plant Diseases Using Deep Learning Algorithm," by Kokatam V. K. R. et al.[9] uses various machine learning algorithms such as Logistic

Regression, K-Nearest Neighbour, Random Forest, Naïve Bayes and Support Vector Machine for detecting disease in different leaves. The dataset comprises images depicting various crops such as tomatoes, potatoes, apples, corn, grapes, and more. Among the tested algorithms, Random Forest achieved the highest accuracy of 95%, followed by Logistic Regression at 90%, K Nearest Neighbors at 92%, Naïve Bayes at 86%, and Support Vector Machine at 77%. Thus, it can be inferred that the Random Forest algorithm is most suitable for analyzing this specific dataset.

III. METHODOLOGY

The objective of the project is to identify the leaf disease by uploading a leaf that has been infected with a disease, the system was put into place, and the disease was identified along with cure recommendation. The classification of plant diseases in the paper is done using ensemble learning model. The various steps for the detection includes :

A. Data Collection

Data collection is a critical step in machine learning, especially when working with specialized domains like agriculture, as in the case of the rice disease dataset. The rice disease dataset contains images of rice leaves affected by two distinct classes of diseases: bacterial leaf blight and brown spot, each comprising 40 leaf images. Each image in the dataset serves as a representation of the specific disease class, providing valuable visual data for training machine learning models. Fig. 1 shows example of each disease from the dataset.

Fig. 1. Sample dataset images

B. Data Processing

The image data undergoes preprocessing, including normalization and augmentation, using TensorFlow's 'ImageDataGenerator'. This prepares the data for training by adjusting its scale and introducing variations such as rotation and shifting. A convolutional neural network (CNN) model is constructed to extract relevant features from the preprocessed images. During training, the model learns to classify images into different categories based on the features it extracts. After training, the model's ability to classify new images is evaluated using techniques such as feature extraction and clustering to map them to specific disease categories.

C. Model training

The CNN architecture, a kind of deep learning model made especially for handling structured data grids like photographs, is used to train the model at first. Its many

layers—convolutional, pooling, and fully connected—allow it to automatically extract features and hierarchical patterns from the input data. Using the fit approach, which iterates through the training data in batches and modifies the model's parameters to minimise the given loss function, the model is trained. Every epoch, the model gains the ability to identify patterns in the input images and adjusts its performance according to the labels supplied. As training proceeds over a number of epochs, the model is able to gradually increase the accuracy of its predictions. The model's capacity for generalisation is evaluated using the validation data. K-means clustering is applied to the output features extracted by the CNN model. An unsupervised machine learning technique called K-means clustering divides a dataset into a fixed number of clusters according on similarity. The algorithm continuously assigns data points to the closest cluster center and refines the centers until they stabilize, leading to clusters characterized by reduced variance within each cluster. By clustering the features, the algorithm groups similar image representations together, potentially improving the model's ability to discriminate between different classes.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Import necessary libraries

Import necessary libraries such as tensorflow, numpy, scikit-learn, matplotlib to facilitate data processing, model training, evaluation and visualization.

```
import numpy as np
import tensorflow as tf
from sklearn.cluster import KMeans
from tensorflow.keras.preprocessing.image import ImageDataGenerator
from tensorflow.keras import layers, models
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler
```

Fig. 2. Importing libraries

B. Image Processing

After importing the necessary libraries, the dataset needs to be loaded. Rice disease dataset from the Kaggle which contain two classes of rice disease Bacterial Leaf Blight and Brown Spot with 40 images each is used. 'ImageDataGenerator' from TensorFlow's Keras is used for image preprocessing and data augmentation. It creates separate generators for training and validation data by specifying the subset parameter, allowing for the efficient loading and processing of image data.

C. Model Training

The processed image is passed to the CNN model for training and evaluation. The CNN model learns to extract features from the input images through its convolutional layers, perform dimensionality reduction using max pooling layers, and make predictions based on the learned features in the final dense layers. The model is compiled using Adam optimizer and is trained using the 'fit' method specifying the training and validation generators, number of epochs, and steps per epoch.

```
model = models.Sequential()
model.add(layers.Conv2D(32, (3, 3), activation='relu', input_shape=(img_size, img_size, 3)))
model.add(layers.MaxPooling2D(2, 2))
model.add(layers.Conv2D(64, (3, 3), activation='relu'))
model.add(layers.MaxPooling2D(2, 2))
model.add(layers.Conv2D(128, (3, 3), activation='relu'))
model.add(layers.MaxPooling2D(2, 2))
model.add(layers.Conv2D(256, (3, 3), activation='relu'))
model.add(layers.MaxPooling2D(2, 2))
model.add(layers.Dropout(0.6))
model.add(layers.Flatten())
model.add(layers.Dense(256, activation='relu', kernel_regularizer=regularizers.l2(0.001)))
model.add(layers.BatchNormalization())
model.add(layers.Dense(train_generator.num_classes, activation='softmax'))
```

Fig. 3. CNN model

D. Applying ensemble

The flattened features from the CNN model are standardized using StandardScaler to ensure consistent scaling across features. K-Means clustering is performed on the scaled training features to partition them into two clusters. The cluster labels are then predicted for the scaled validation features. Finally, the predicted cluster labels are mapped to class labels based on majority voting within each cluster. The trained model is then saved as 'model.h5' file.

```
train_features = model.predict(train_generator)
val_features = model.predict(validation_generator)
train_features_flatten = train_features.reshape(train_features.shape[0], -1)
val_features_flatten = val_features.reshape(val_features.shape[0], -1)
scaler = StandardScaler()
train_features_scaled = scaler.fit_transform(train_features_flatten)
val_features_scaled = scaler.transform(val_features_flatten)
kmeans_model = KMeans(n_clusters=2, random_state=42)
kmeans_model.fit(train_features_scaled)
val_clusters = kmeans_model.predict(val_features_scaled)
cluster_to_class_mapping = {0: 0, 1: 1}
val_pred = [cluster_to_class_mapping[cluster] for cluster in val_clusters]
```

Fig. 4. K-Means Clustering

E. Model Testing

The Streamlit web application is used for classifying rice leaf diseases using a pre-trained CNN model. It allows users to upload an image of a leaf, preprocesses the image, predicts the class label using the model, and displays the predicted class along with the classification accuracy. Additionally, it provides remedies for the predicted disease class based on a predefined mapping.

```
def preprocess_and_predict(image):
    image = image.resize((img_size, img_size))
    image_array = np.array(image) / 255.0
    image_array = np.expand_dims(image_array, axis=0)
    features = model.predict(image_array)
    features_flatten = features.reshape(features.shape[0], -1)
    scaled_features = scaler.transform(features_flatten)
    cluster = kmeans_model.predict(scaled_features)
    class_index = cluster_to_class_mapping[cluster[0]]
    return class_index
```

Fig. 5. Preprocessing user input image

V. RESULT

The study depicts a system for identifying leaf diseases in rice plants through image analysis, providing recommendations for treatment. The approach utilized ensemble learning models, specifically a convolutional neural network (CNN), for classification. Data preprocessing

involved normalization and augmentation using TensorFlow's ImageDataGenerator, preparing the dataset for training. The CNN model was trained iteratively using the fit method, with validation data used to prevent overfitting. Additionally, K-means clustering was applied to the extracted features to enhance the model's discrimination capabilities. Fig. 6. depicts the user interface to upload the image of the leaf to predict whether the leaf has disease.

Rice Leaf Disease Classification

Fig. 6. Interface predicting the disease

A. Analysis

The results of the CNN model training and validation samples showed an accuracy of 50%, indicating a need to address potential overfitting issues. To mitigate overfitting, K-means clustering was implemented to enhance the model's generalization capabilities. This additional step aimed to improve the model's ability to discern patterns and accurately classify rice types, thus addressing the observed discrepancy in accuracy between training and validation samples. Fig 7. represents the performance metrics of the model.

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Bacterial leaf blight	0.70	0.88	0.78	8
Brown spot	0.83	0.62	0.71	8
accuracy			0.75	16
macro avg	0.77	0.75	0.75	16
weighted avg	0.77	0.75	0.75	16

Accuracy: 75%

Fig. 7. Performance metrics of the model

A table called the confusion matrix is frequently used to explain how well a classification model performs when applied to a set of test data whose real values are known. The model's confusion matrix is shown in Fig. 8. In the matrix, the examples in a predicted class are represented by each column, and the occurrences in an actual class are represented by each row.

Fig. 8. Confusion matrix

B. Comparison

Ramesh S. et al.[12] developed a model for plant disease classification utilizing papaya leaves with a Random Forest classifier achieving an accuracy of 70%. The labeled datasets are segregated into training and testing data, with feature vectors generated for the training dataset using HoG feature extraction. These feature vectors are then utilized to train a Random Forest classifier. Additionally, the feature vector generation process is applied to the testing data, and the resulting feature vectors are used for prediction by the trained classifier. This approach ensures that the model is trained and evaluated on distinct datasets, minimizing the risk of overfitting and providing a reliable assessment of its performance. In contrast, the model proposed in this study employs ensemble learning techniques and achieves a higher accuracy of 75%.The model is first trained using the CNN model and the features extracted is passed to the K-Means Clustering to reduce the overfitting issues.

VI.CONCLUSION

The study focuses on predicting rice leaf diseases utilizing leaf images. It employs an ensemble method combining CNN and K-means clustering. In addition to disease prediction, the study also forecasts remedies for the identified diseases, contributing to comprehensive plant health management strategies. The future scope of the study include predicting the stages of the disease along with the most efficient methods to cure the disease. This holistic approach not only aids in early detection and accurate diagnosis but also enables timely and targeted treatment, ultimately leading to improved crop yield and agricultural sustainability.

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